

D2.1 RDA RESULTS, ADOPTION AND TAKE-UP REPORT

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Abstract	This is an interim report on the activities undertaken to promote, support and encourage the take-up of RDA outputs and recommendations. It will be updated in the final month of RDA Europe 4.0.

Dissemination Level

- PU: Public
- PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)

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1 Introduction and Executive Summary

This report describes take-up and adoption of work produced by RDA and, more specifically, the role of the RDA Europe 4 project in promoting such take-up and adoption. It is the first of two reports which will cover this topic; the second report is due in May 2020.

The Research Data Alliance has 30 Recommendations and Supporting Outputs, 8 of which are officially acknowledged as ICT Technical Specifications, with several more in the process of endorsement. A full list can be seen on the RDA website.¹ Many actions have been taken by RDA Europe to increase the adoption of outputs; they include an open call to award grants to adoption projects, publishing adoption stories online and in a special collection of the CODATA Data Science journal, and illustrating examples in webinars. RDA Europe Ambassadors are encouraged to support adoption and RDA Nodes have specific KPIs in this area. In addition, the RDA Secretariat has convened an Adoption Task Force which is developing use cases to support adoption and assigning DOIs to track the uptake of outputs – the RDA Europe project plays a key role in this activity.

Details of all of these activities are described in the sections which follow.

2 Supporting European take-up and adoption

RDA Europe adoption grants call

Adoption of new technology or processes can involve uncertain costs, particularly for early adopters who cannot draw on the experience of others. This is one barrier to early adoption of RDA work which then becomes a barrier to adoption in general, since many will rely on the reports and experience of early adopters in order to make adoption decisions. Earlier RDA Europe projects recognised this and provided adoption grants as a means to overcome this barrier. This work has been continued and improved in the current project. Adoption grants are one of the instruments put in place by the project to stimulate take up and adoption of RDA outputs and recommendations. The adoption grants projects will provide a valuable testbed and a widest audience for dissemination and training on RDA outputs and recommendations. Successful applicants are required to make information available on their adoption experience.

Building on the adoption grants offered by the previous RDA Europe project, a single grant call was developed under the remit of RDA Europe 4.0². This drew lessons from past programmes; we placed new requirements on applications and we made alterations to the evaluation process. Specifically, we required that applicants make outputs openly available and should have sufficient knowledge of the outputs to undertake adoption without support from WG Chairs. In the evaluation process, we aimed for a disciplinary balance across the portfolio of funded projects. Useful advice was also provided on the contracting procedure.

The call for adoption grants opened in December 2018 and closed in March 2019. A total amount of €120,000 was allocated in the project budget, permitting 8 projects of up to €15,000 each. The project used a range of mechanisms to promote the call. As well as promotion through social media and on the RDA website, it was promoted in the RDA Newsletter and

¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/all-recommendations-and-outputs>

² <https://grants.rd-alliance.org/OpenCalls/call-europe-adoption-grants>

featured in presentations given by project staff and national node members. A webinar was held on 21st February to promote the call. The DCC (UEDIN) presented on the programme and gave advice to prospective applicants. Presentations were also given by DANS³ and VADMC⁴ on their adoption cases, and a Q&A session was moderated at the end. 43 participants attended. Slides and video are available on the RDA website.⁵

13 applications for these grants were received from 9 different countries. A strong range of proposals were put forward, covering a range of outputs and disciplines. 8 awards were made as listed below. We are currently working with applicants to agree announcements about projects.

Table 1 - funded adoption grant proposals

Project title	Country	Output(s) being adopted
23 Things Revisited: Field guides to research data management	Netherlands	23 Things: Libraries For Research Data
From Portal To PIDs: Creating Persistent Identifiers For MERIL-2 RI Entries	France	Persistent identifiers: Consolidated assertions
Implementing a data publishing workflow model for research data sharing in ICTP	Italy	Data Type Model and Registry Workflows for Research Data Publishing: Models and Key Components The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations: Interlinking Standards, Databases and Data Policies Eleven Quick Tips for Finding Research Data
Title TBC - merged proposal	Hungary	Workflows for Research Data Publishing: Models and Key Components Repository Audit and Certification Catalogues
CCCA Subset & Dynamic Data Citation Service	Austria	Scalable Dynamic-data Citation Methodology

³ The Dutch Data archiving and Networked Services

⁴ The Virtual Atomic and Molecular Data Centre

⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/what-why-and-how-rda-europe-40-adoption-grants-0>

Project title	Country	Output(s) being adopted
Improving the Copernicus Climate Data Store metadata scheme with the “RDA metadata standards repository”	Spain	Metadata Standards Directory
Template for reproducible, shareable and achievable data analysis	Spain	Workflows for Research Data Publishing: Models and Key Components
A model of data integration related to wheat genetic resources and resistance to Fusarium head blight	Bulgaria	Wheat Data Interoperability Guidelines, Ontologies and User Cases

The outputs and impact of the adoption grants projects will be reported in D2.3 Final RDA Results, Adoption & Take-Up Report due on Month 27 (May 2020).

A brief summary of each adoption project is presented here.

2.1.1 23 Things Revisited: Field guides to research data management

Research support staff, such as data stewards, IT support staff, librarians or policy officers, often have different levels of understanding of RDM. However, they need to collaborate closely to offer state-of-the-art support for researchers wishing to do responsible RDM. The 23 Things can act as a shared reference tool that enhances mutual understanding and improves collaboration. It can also be used for quick reference and as a guideline for training. We propose to update and adjust the 23 Things to the above mentioned audiences and stimulate nationwide adoption.

2.1.2 A model of data integration related to wheat genetic resources and resistance to Fusarium head blight

The adoption of recommendations from RDA Wheat Data Interoperability initiative can be addressed to better access, share, store and analyse all wheat related data used by the research community. The main goal of our proposal is to develop a model for semantic interoperability which will integrate the data from the existing resources with the existing external open source web based knowledge sources for Fusarium Head Blight (FHB) knowledge discovery.

2.1.3 CCCA Subset & Dynamic Data Citation Service

The Climate Change Centre Austria, as research data infrastructure facility for the Climatological Domain, targets a very limited user community. The implementation of Scalable Dynamic-data Citation Methodology aims to extend the implemented Service to further research domain, the Earth Observation Sciences.

2.1.4 From Portal To PIDs: Creating Persistent Identifiers For MERIL-2 RI Entries

The implementation of the data publishing workflow is connected to the technical development of the data repository at the University of Debrecen, to be launched at the end of 2019.

Introduction of the data publishing workflow is beneficiary for all researchers as users will be educated about standards and international guidelines (FAIR, FORCE) necessary for data sharing and the institutional data repository will be used as a publishing platforms for data outputs.

2.1.5 Implementing a data publishing workflow model for research data sharing in International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP)

This proposal constitutes the Pilot Project and first use case of adoption of the ICTP's Data Sharing Initiative. It will make available to scientists around the world global single station calibrated Ionospheric Total Electron Content data. The calibration will be a single station technique developed in ICTP that allows to work at different scales, from local to regional and global.

2.1.6 Improving the Copernicus Climate Data Store metadata scheme with the "RDA metadata standards repository"

The [Climate Data Store](#) repository contains various types of data for which we have to present summaries at the level of variable and dataset. Adopting and presenting the RDA metadata repository as a trustful reference and using the various standards gathered there will help us make strong recommendations on what should be presented in the CDS.

2.1.7 Learning to share: a road to national data publishing policy and the Hungarian data repository evaluation

These two proposals from Hungary will be merged into one use-case project. In lack of institutional or national standards in Hungary, RDA Outputs including the technical and social infrastructure solutions provide the necessary support and guidance to start implementing and coordinating data management practices on different levels. In addition establishing data repositories is an increasingly urgent task in Hungary. With the adoption of RDA Recommendation Repository Audit and Certification Catalogues the [Library and Information Centre of Hungarian Academy of Sciences](#) aims to unchain the Hungarian repository revolution: new data repositories will established, the existing ones will be standardised and they will use similar workflows.

The CODATA Data Science Journal - RDA Results Special Collection

The original grant proposal contained a number of calls for papers on adoption to be published in special issues of the CODATA Data Science Journal⁶; funding from the project would be used to pay publication charges which would otherwise fall on the authors or their places of work. This process has been amended to an open, continuous call which will run for most of the duration of the project to meet the requirements given by the DSJ publication workflow. The CODATA journal's publication mechanisms will allow these papers to be viewed as a special collection.

The submitted manuscripts can cover topics such as:

- The results (RDA Recommendations, Supporting Outputs or Other Outputs) produced by an Interest or Working Group;
- The description of an Adoption Case outlining how a specific recommendation or output has been implemented in a given use case;

⁶ <http://www.codata.org/publications/data-science-journal>

- Other types of work related to RDA activities.

The special collection is continuously advertised via the RDA website and social network and specific promotional activities are done during the Plenary Meetings and via the RDA newsletter, mailing lists and National Node pages on RDA website. A special “card” has been designed for the RDA special collection. A dedicated page⁷ on the web site has been set up to inform the members about the scope of the collection and submission mechanism, as well as to inform about the article processing charge (APC) cost covered by the RDA Europe 4.0 project.

The special collection call was launched in July 2018, and the first paper was published in January 2019. A dedicated page⁸ on DSJ website was designed for the RDA collection and contains information about the special collection scope and indications for submission. Published papers to date are as follows:

- Wu, M., Psomopoulos, F., Khalsa, S.J. and de Waard, A., 2019. Data Discovery Paradigms: User Requirements and Recommendations for Data Repositories. Data Science Journal, 18(1), p.3. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2019-003>
879 views | 222 downloads | 59 tweets (as of 13 May 2019)
- Zwölf, C.M., Moreau, N., Ba, Y.-A. and Dubernet, M.-L., 2019. Implementing in the VAMDC the New Paradigms for Data Citation from the Research Data Alliance. Data Science Journal, 18(1), p.4. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2019-004>
188 views | 26 downloads | 20 tweets (as of 13 May 2019)
- Cousijn, H., Feeney, P., Lowenberg, D., Presani, E. and Simons, N., 2019. Bringing Citations and Usage Metrics Together to Make Data Count. Data Science Journal, 18(1), p.9. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2019-009>
958 views | 216 downloads | 78 tweets (as of 13 May 2019)

So far we have received 9 proposals for submission to the RDA special collection, of which 3 have been published, 3 rejected or redirected to other DSJ selections and 3 are in other stages of the publication workflow. We are in a position to support around 30 publications in total. The three published manuscripts were received in July-August 2018 and published in January-March 2019 indicating that it takes 4-6 months for the publication process. As such we plan a concerted promotion drive in summer 2019 to ensure we have received significantly more manuscripts by the Helsinki plenary in October 2019. This plenary will be the last promotion opportunity to realistically get papers to print by project close, though of course we will continue to accept and review submitted manuscripts until May 2020. We are instituting more frequent monitoring of the submission and review process with the editorial team at CNR in order to be able to take corrective action to increase submission rates more rapidly in the coming months.

The Data Science Journal special collection aims to gather and promote research results and outcomes stemming from the Research Data Alliance activities. In particular, it collects high quality papers describing the latest results of RDA working groups (WGs) or interest groups (IGs) focusing particularly on use cases that highlight the added value of the RDA solutions for different challenges related to research data sharing and management.

⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/call-papers-research-data-alliance-results-special-collection>

⁸ <https://datascience.codata.org/collections/special/research-data-alliance-results/>

Adoption stories

Producing a journal article is attractive to some adopters as a way of gaining attention for their work and improving their own scholarly reputation. However, these incentives do not exist for all adopters and for others the effort involved may not be justified. We therefore offer more lightweight mechanisms for sharing information about the adoption and use of RDA outputs, such as adoption stories shared via the RDA website. This activity is carried out in partnership with the RDA Secretariat, described in the next section.

KPI 2.4 relates to this work, and anticipates 10 new adoption stories being generated during the RDA Europe 4.0 project. 5 have already been published, and 6 more are due to be published in late May and early June 2019, meaning that this KPI will have been exceeded. We intend nonetheless to continue to encourage more to be written.

3 Inputs to RDA secretariat adoption activities

The RDA Secretariat coordinates efforts across the organisation to drive adoption. RDA Secretariat adoption support has three related and underlying aims:

1. Enhancing the findability and intelligibility of outputs
2. Supporting adoption through education and training
3. Monitoring adoption stories and impact

The activities undertaken during RDA Europe 4 include:

- Webinars to provide training on the use of specific RDA outputs. This activity began recently, with the first webinar in March 2019 dealing with “Outputs to Support Reproducible Health Research”. It drew on positive experiences of similar webinars organised at more local level. The webinar recording is available on YouTube <https://youtu.be/JPHfLcQscds>
- At RDA Plenaries 12 and 13, a session on RDA Outputs included moderated discussions between several adopters in a panel format. These sessions aimed to share experiences between adopters and the wider community regarding the process, impact and challenges of adopting RDA Recommendations and Outputs. The P13 session covered:
 - Outreach overview of all RDA outputs, structured according to solutions given
 - Lightning talks of chairs of Agrisemantics WG, PID Kernel Information WG and Data Fitness for Use WG
 - Adopters of the Outputs of these 3 WGs will be on the panel to tell their adoption stories along these lines:
 - What is the **impact** of working with RDA Recommendations for your community?
 - Can you share examples of how adoption has led to improvements in community practice? (or improvements you expect to see)
 - What **challenges** did you experience in adopting the RDA Recommendations? What advice would you offer to other potential adopters?

- Production of an overview presentation on all RDA Recommendations and Outputs grouped thematically according to the research data lifecycle⁹. This activity was first trialled at the most recent RDA plenary (P13, Philadelphia).
- At RDA Plenary 13, two Birds of a Feather sessions focused on adoption were run to collect community feedback on the process of adopting RDA outputs¹⁰ and the dissemination of adoption experiences¹¹.
- The collecting and dissemination of adoption stories: “an opportunity for individuals, organisations and projects who have adopted RDA outputs to share their experiences and lessons learned.” These are made available through the RDA website¹². The Secretariat actively collects such stories but also allows for independent submission through a web form¹³. The web form is designed to streamline the process of collecting stories and reduce the time required for publication.
- A survey to gather information on what the community needs to make RDA output adoption feasible. This survey will close on 3 June.
- The Secretariat has also worked to publicise its activities to increase take-up at plenaries and node events. Dissemination methods have included a video on adopting RDA outputs, posters on adoption activities at RDA plenaries, postcards and flyers.

⁹ https://www.rd-alliance.org/sites/default/files/attachment/RDA%20Outputs_RDA%20Adoption%20Business%20Session_final-2.pptx

¹⁰ <https://rd-alliance.org/bof-rda-adoption-making-rda-outputs-and-recommendations-easier-adopt-rda-13th-plenary-meeting>

¹¹ <https://rd-alliance.org/bof-rda-adoption-enhanced-dissemination-adoption-stories-rda-13th-plenary-meeting>

¹² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/adoption-stories>

¹³ <https://rd-alliance.org/add/adoption-stories>

Figure 1 - postcards promoting adoption at P13

4 RDA Europe National Nodes

Established as part of the RDA Europe 4.0 project, the RDA national nodes¹⁴ in European countries engage with research communities, support national agendas, and aim to increase the uptake of standards and participation in RDA globally. As part of their workplans, all nodes are mandated to foster the adoption of RDA outputs in their regions. This aspect of their work includes outreach to local institutions and national infrastructures to encourage the submission of adoption stories to the RDA Secretariat and articles to the CODATA Data Science Journal special collection on RDA results.

Adoption activities of the national nodes, including KPIs in this area, are monitored and reported via quarterly reports, monthly node coordination calls and a living spreadsheet tracking all outputs and adoption stories at both global and national node levels. To date, outreach efforts of the RDA Europe National Nodes have resulted in five adoption stories, with further submissions in progress. The stories already published¹⁵ report on the adoption experiences of five organisations:

- Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS) adoption of the CoreTrustSeal Data Repository certification
- Strasbourg astronomical Data Centre (CDS) adoption of the CoreTrustSeal Data Repository certification

¹⁴ <https://rd-alliance.org/rda-europe>

¹⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/adoption-stories>

- The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development adoption of RDA outputs related to Income Streams for Data Repositories
- The French National Institute for Agricultural Research (INRA) adoption of multiple RDA outputs
- The Virtual Atomic and Molecular Data Centre (VAMDC) adoption of RDA recommendations for data citation and the Scholix service for exchanging information about links between literature and data. This adoption case was also documented in greater detail in a CODATA Data Science Journal article¹⁶.

The nodes have a common KPI to assist in the collection of such stories. All those published so far come from the work of the nodes in France and The Netherlands. As noted above, 6 more adoption stories are scheduled for publication by mid-June 2019, of which 3 are European and have emerged as the result of work of the European nodes.

5 RDA Ambassadors

Outreach around adoption has also been supported through the RDA EU Ambassadors programme¹⁷. Selected domain Ambassadors who are also group co-chairs or actively involved in discipline focused RDA Working and Interest groups have outlined activities in their work plan focused on supporting adoption in their communities of practice. Examples include:

- Caterina Caracciolo, Ambassador for the Agricultural Sciences, co-chair of the RDA Agrisemantics WG and contributor to the Wheat Data WG - working with the FAO, e-Rosa project (e-Infrastructure Roadmaps for Open Science in Agricultural and Food Sciences) and GODAN.
- Julien Barde, Ambassador for Marine Sciences and co-chair of the Fisheries Data Interoperability WG makes the case in his grant proposal for the development of factsheets for adoption stories together with other Fisheries domain resources (data, code and generic workflows)
- Sebastien Denvil - Ambassador for the Earth Sciences and Climate modelling has identified the CMIP6 analysis period taking place in 2019 and 2020 as a particularly favourable moment to engage the climate data practitioners, data producers and data service providers and highlight the potential of RDA outputs for the requirements of the wider climate community.
- Ana Slavec - Ambassador for Engineering / Renewable Materials is collaborating with the RDA Materials Resource Registries WG on an update to the report produced by the group on the metadata standards for different materials that in its initial version doesn't acknowledge wood and other biomaterials.

The Ambassadors have started their work in February 2019. The results and impact of their activities will be reported in deliverable D2.3.

¹⁶ <http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2019-004>

¹⁷ <https://grants.rd-alliance.org/node/804>, <https://grants.rd-alliance.org/OpenCalls/call-ambassadors-i-wave>

6 Transforming RDA recommendations into standards for public procurement

In many contexts, formal recognition of a technical specification through a recognised standards process is a necessary prerequisite to adoption. It can, for instance, make it more straightforward to include use of such specifications in an IT procurement process. This was recognised by the predecessor project, RDA Europe 3, which began the process of identifying suitable candidate RDA Outputs and Recommendations for submission to the European Multi-Stakeholders Platform on ICT Standardisation¹⁸. 8 candidate RDA recommendations were put forward in two waves, all of which have received approval, although the second wave have yet to be formally confirmed through publication as a Commission decision. RDA Europe 4.0 began work on identifying candidates for a third wave of submissions in September 2018 and has identified 4 more promising candidates for submission that will be discussed in the next meeting of the European Multi-Stakeholders Platform taking place in June 2019. On the advice of the Commission, RDA Europe 4.0 is awaiting publication of the results of the previous wave before taking the process further. The timelines and candidate specifications are described more fully in deliverable D3.2 “INTERIM ICT TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS”.

- TS1 Data Foundation & Terminology Model*
- TS2 PID Information Types API- Persistent Identifier Type Registry*
- TS3 Data Type Registries Model*
- TS4 Practical Policies recommendations*
- TS5 Dynamic-data Citation Methodology**
- TS6 Data Description Registry Interoperability Model**
- TS7 RDA/WDS Repository Audit and Certification Catalogues**
- TS8 RDA/WDS Publishing Data Services**
- TS9 Research Data Repository Interoperability Recommendations***
- TS10 Research Data Collections API ***
- TS11 RDA/WDS Workflows for Research Data Publishing Model***
- TS12 Wheat Data Interoperability Recommendation***

**Approved and published in the Official Journal of the European Union “COMMISSION IMPLEMENTING DECISION (EU) 2017/1358” of 20 July 2017 on the identification of ICT Technical Specifications for referencing in public procurement <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32017D1358>;*

***Approved and awaiting publication.*

**** Beginning submission phase in June 2019*

¹⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/european-multi-stakeholder-platform-ict-standardisation>

7 Conclusions

The first 13 months of the projects were crucial to set the scene and the procedures to stimulate adoption of the RDA recommendations and outputs. In addition to all the contributions brought to the global adoption activities, specific instruments have been set up in Europe to stimulate take up, including adoption projects, ambassadors and nodes cascading grants mechanisms and targeted outreach and communications activities. We now have good examples of adoption being encouraged and promoted by activities at national level, supported and nurtured by the European project.

At month 14, the following European adoption stories have been produced or will shortly be available:

- **OpenAire** adopted RDA/WDS Publishing Data Services WG Outputs and the Scholix Interoperability Framework.
- **Virtual Atomic and Molecular Data Center (VAMDC, France)** adopted Dynamic Data Citation Recommendation and Scholix. The authors of the adoption story also published an article in the CODATA special collection on RDA: <http://http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2019-004>
- **French National Institute for Agricultural Research (INRA, France)** adopted Wheat Data Interoperability Guidelines, Agrisemantics Working Group recommendations, Recommendations for Implementing a Virtual Layer for Management of the Complete Life Cycle of Scientific Data, 23 Things: Libraries for Research Data, The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations and Data Citation of Evolving data.
- **Organisation for Economic and Co-operation and Development (OECD)** adopted Income Streams for Data Repositories
- **Climate Change Center Austria** adopted Dynamic Data Citation Recommendation
- **DANS** adopted Core Trust Seal
- **Strasbourg astronomical Data Centre (CDS, France)** adopted Core Trust Seal.

These stories demonstrate adoption of different outputs by different communities and put the basis for engagement of a wider RDA audience.

One area that has fallen short of expectations is the publicising of adoption via journal papers, a route that we had thought would be attractive to those for whom peer-reviewed publication is a success criterion. We will be monitoring this area more closely in the coming months to understand if it would be wise to redirect some of the resources allocated to this activity elsewhere.

The ICT Technical specifications, remain one of the best showcase of the impact of the work of RDA and are a concrete example of how RDA can shape the European ICT public procurement and concretely contribute to the European Open Science Cloud, that will require best practices and standards in the near future.